

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Cation	H ⁺	UO ₂ ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
log K ₁	11.40	9.60	8.83	8.45	7.87	7.81	7.72	5.63
log K ₂	—	8.84	7.27	—	6.76	—	—	—

For H⁺, K₁ corresponds to the species LH, while for metal ion K₁ and K₂ correspond to species ML and ML₂ respectively.

The metal ligand titration curve was found to be well separated from the titration curve which indicates that the liberation of proton from the phenolic 'OH' group is due to chelation.

The stability constants of metal complexes of this ligand fall in the order UO₂²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Cd²⁺ > Mg²⁺, in agreement with the Irving-Williams order¹¹.

References

1. J. BJERRUM, 'Metal Ammine Formations in Aqueous Solutions' P. Hassø and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
2. S. L. GARG and K. K. PANDE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 771.
3. S. L. GARG and K. K. PANDE, Paper presented at Convention of Chemists (1969). The Indian Chemical Society.
4. H. IRVING and H.S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
5. JAMES C. DUFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 547.
6. A. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry', III Edition, Longmans, London, p. 177.
7. G. SCHWARZENBACH, 'Complexometric Titrations', Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1956, p. 60.
8. A. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', III Edition, Longmans, London, 1961, p. 539.
9. H. M. N. H. IRVING and U. S. MAHNOT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 1215.
10. K. ECKSCHLAGER, 'Errors, Measurements and Results in Chemical Analysis', (Ed. R. A. Chalmers), Van Nostrand Reinhold Co. Ltd., London, 1969, p. 86.
11. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.

Some New Antifungal Triazolyl Sulphides

R B PATHAK and S. C. BAHTEL*

Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur (U P.)

Manuscript received 14 May 1979, revised 29 August 1980, accepted 23 February 1981

3-Amino-1,2,4-triazole (Amizole) is a commercial herbicide. Many compounds having triazole ring have been reported to exhibit fungicidal^{1,2}, insecticidal^{3,4} and pesticidal^{5,6} properties. The SH group attached

to the heterocyclic nucleus may enhance the fungicidal⁷ activity. The sulphides have been reported to be more biologically active than parent mercapto compounds⁸. Further, heterocyclic sulphides have been known to possess significant antifungal⁹ activity. Pesticidal activity of bis (4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl) alkanes has revealed that activity increased¹⁰ with the increase of number of methylene groups. In view of this, the above title compounds have been synthesised to study their antifungal activity.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Aryloxyacetyl hydrazines :

These were prepared by the method of Conti¹¹.

1-Aryloxyacetyl-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides¹² :

These were prepared by the reaction of aryloxyacetyl hydrazines and arylisothiocyanates.

3-Aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles¹³ :

These have been prepared by alkaline cyclisation of corresponding thiosemicarbazides.

Bis-(3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-1, 2, 4-triazol-5-yl)-disulphides(I) :

To an ice-cold ethanolic solution (25 ml) of 3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazole (0.01M), a cold ethanolic solution (25 ml) of bromine (0.005M) was added dropwise with swirling. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

Bis-(3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-ethylene disulphides(II) :

To an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of 3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (0.01M), sodium acetate (2.0 g) and ethylene dibromide (0.005M) were added. The contents were refluxed for 4 hrs and then poured into water. The solid separating was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 2.

Fungicidal activity :

All the eighteen compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus* and *A. niger* by agar plate technique^{13,14} at three different concentrations namely 1:1,000, 1:10,000 and 1:100,000. All the compounds possess moderate fungicidal activity.

In general, compounds having chlorine or methoxy group were found to show higher antifungal activity. The ethylene disulphides were much better than the corresponding sulphides with respect to their fungicidal

NOTES

TABLE 1—Bis-(3-ARYLOXYMETHYL-4-ARYL-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-5-YL)-DISULPHIDES (I)

S. No.	R	R ₁	m. p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N%		S%		% inhibition at 1:100,000	
						Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
1 ^a	H	4-Cl	242	81.5	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	12.88	13.23	10.26	10.11	47.8	39.4
2	H	4-CH ₃	48	98.3	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	—	—	11.02	10.81	38.7	36.2
3	H	2-OCH ₃	152	76.9	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	—	—	10.47	10.25	45.6	40.7
4	2-CH ₃	2-CH ₃	120	87.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	13.20	13.54	10.55	10.32	40.3	38.0
5	2-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	201	87.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	—	—	10.05	9.81	50.5	40.8
6	3-CH ₃	4-Cl	130	85.7	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	—	—	9.94	9.68	52.7	46.0
7	3-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	54	97.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	—	—	10.54	10.32	38.6	38.4
8	3-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	85	85.2	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	12.51	12.88	10.02	9.81	49.3	39.5
9	4-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	96	87.2	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	—	—	10.06	9.81	50.9	42.8
10	2-Cl	2-CH ₃	116	85.4	C ₁₂ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	—	—	9.92	9.68	44.8	42.2
11	2-Cl	2-OCH ₃	138	71.3	C ₁₂ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	11.80	12.12	9.49	9.23	51.5	46.8
12	4-Cl	2-OCH ₃	175	80.3	C ₁₂ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	—	—	9.48	9.23	52.4	47.3

Ir spectral data ν_{max} in cm^{-1}

	conjugated C=N	<i>p</i> -disubstituted benzene	—C-O-C—	C-Cl
a	1600	826	1230	755

TABLE 2—Bis-(3-ARYLOXYMETHYL-4-ARYL-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-5-YL)-ETHYLENE DISULPHIDES (II)

S. No.	R	R ₁	m. p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N%		S%		% inhibition at 1:100,000 concn.	
						Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
13	H	2-OCH ₃	49-50	85.8	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	12.54	12.88	10.02	9.81	48.2	43.5
14	2-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	31	82.6	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	—	—	9.64	9.41	51.3	45.8
15	3-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	54	86.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	—	—	9.66	9.41	51.0	45.2
16	4-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	56	88.9	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	—	—	9.67	9.41	54.4	50.6
17	2-Cl	2-OCH ₃	48	78.7	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	11.29	11.65	9.09	8.87	55.7	52.9
18 ^b	4-Cl	2-OCH ₃	51	82.2	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	—	—	9.12	8.87	60.2	54.3

Ir spectral data ν_{max} in cm^{-1}

	conjugated C=N	<i>p</i> -disubstituted benzene	C-S-C	—C-O-C—	C-Cl
b	1580	830	735	1250	760

activity. The most active compounds of the series were 6, 11, 12 and 16 to 18.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur and Dr. Y. B. Singh, Principal, St. Andrew's College, Gorakhpur for providing the necessary facilities.

References

1. S. A. GREENFIELD, M. C. SEIDEL and W. C. VONMEYER, *Ger. Offen.*, 1, 966, 806 (1974); *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, 82, 150485u.
2. W. KRAEMER, K. H. BUECHEL, W. BRANDES and P. E. FROBERGER, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 334, 352, (1975); *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, 82, 170967f.
3. G. TANAKA, *Japan Kokai*, 74, 95, 973 (1974); *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, 82, 156320h.
4. T. I. WAKINS and D. M. WEIGHTON, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 530, 287, (1976); *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, 84, 135677f.
5. B. BOEHNER, W. MEYER and D. DAWES, *Swiss.*, 573, 206, (1976); *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, 84, 180232t.
6. L. GSELL and W. MEYER, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 739, 084, (1978); *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, 88, 190844r.
7. J. G. HORSFALL and S. RICH, *Contributions Boyce Thomsom Institute*, 1951, 16, 316.
8. K. C. JOSHI and A. B. SEN, *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 1952, 11, 526.
9. U. SRIVASTAVA, R. H. KHAN and S. C. BAHTEL, *J. Antibact. Antifung. Agents (Japan)*, 1979, 7, 8.
10. CHIMETRON S.a.r.l., *Fr.*, 1, 476, 543, (1967); *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 69, 96725p.
11. L. CONTI, *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, 61, 4253e.
12. R. B. PATHAK, (Miss) B. JAHAN and S.C. BAHTEL, *J. Antibact. Antifung. Agents (Japan)*, 1980, 8, 12.
13. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 11, 357.
14. U.S.D.A. Circular No. 198 (1931).

Chemical Examination of Essential Oil of *Tagetes minuta* Linn.

R. K. BASLAS⁺ and ASHOK KUMAR SINGH

Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry,
Govt. Raza P. G. College, (Rohilkhand
University), Rampur-244 901 (U.P.)

Manuscript received 22 September 1980, accepted
23 February 1981

PLANT—*Tagetes minuta* Linn. (Family Compositae).

Isolation procedure—Steam distillation (Yield 0.8%).

Physical constants—Sp. gravity 0.8731, n_D^{25} 1.5896, $(\alpha)_D^{25} +4.67$, acid value-2.3218, ester value 53.69, ester value after acetylation 134.87 and carbonyl value as $C_{10}H_{16}O$ -27.08%

Previous work—Few workers¹⁻³ have reported the chemistry of essential oil from flowering tops and separated phenolic and non-phenolic terpenes of the oil.

Different constituents of the oil were separated by Kiesel gel column using the solvent benzene-ethyl acetate (95:5). The identified terpenes have been listed in Table 1. Ir spectra were obtained on Perkin-Elmer

TABLE 1

Compounds	Yield	Methods of identification
Aromendrene	23.90	ir. nmr, n_D^{25} 1.4647, Co-TLC, and GLC.
α -Pinene	0.96	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.46627, nopinic acid ⁴ , Co-TLC and GLC.
β -Phellandrene	1.04	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.4787, Co-TLC and GLC.
d-Limonene	9.60	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.4746, Co-TLC and GLC.
Ocimene	13.10	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.4857, Co-TLC and GLC.
β -Myrcene	16.40	ir, n_D^{25} - 1.4889, Co-TLC and GLC.
Caryophyllene	0.36	ir, Co-TLC and GLC.
p-Cymene	0.43	ir, Co-TLC and GLC.
Tagetone	15.10	ir, Methyl isobutyl ketone adducts.* Co-TLC and GLC.
d-Carvone	6.10	ir, Co-TLC and GLC.
Linalool	3.60	ir, n_D^{25} -1.4624, Co-TLC and GLC.
Linalylacetate	4.30	ir, n_D^{25} -1.6327, Co-TLC and GLC.
Eugenol	0.47	ir, Co-TLC and GLC.

* All the melting points of derivatives were compared with the melting points given by Guenther.